

Carbon Farming and Agroforestry

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Alley cropping at Lill-Nägels Agroforestry Pilot farm in Finland (Photo: Tanja Kähkönen).

In carbon farming, practices that increase carbon sequestration and stocks in forests and soils, or that decrease greenhouse gas emissions from soils, are used. The European Union has included agroforestry as one of the measures for carbon farming in the Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming (CRCF) Regulation (EU/2024/3012). CRCF Regulation is the first *European Union* wide voluntary framework for certifying carbon farming, carbon removals and carbon storage. As CRCF Regulation establishes *European Union* wide quality criteria, monitoring and reporting processes can facilitate solutions and investments in carbon farming after certification schemes are recognised.

Studies assessing the potential for carbon farming and agroforestry are rare in *Finland*. Whereas carbon sequestration rates are generally lower in northern climates, there are vast areas of farmland with low tree presence of trees which gives plenty of room for planting additional trees or enhance natural regeneration. Similar agroforestry systems as found in *Finland* can sequester 2.6 Mg C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ in riparian buffer zones, 3.4 Mg C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ in agrisilvicultural (i.e. alley cropping) systems and 6.1 Mg C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ for silvopastures in *North America and Canada*. Research in northern Europe has shown that agroforestry can enhance both soil carbon and above-ground biomass, which will offset the relatively low sequestration rates in monocrop agricultural land without trees.

In agroforestry, multiple environmental benefits are created in the same land area. Carbon farming practices, such as cover crop, reduced tillage, and organic amendments enhance carbon sequestration in soil and vegetation while improving soil health and productivity. Agroforestry practices such as agrisilvicultural including alley cropping, windbreaks, riparian buffers and silvopasture including forest grazing can complement carbon farming by fostering biodiversity, enhancing nutrient cycling, increasing resilience against extreme weather events (such as drought, strong winds, heavy rain, flooding) and creating diverse income streams for farmers.

References

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